

DEVELOPMENTS IN HOLLOW POLYACRYLONITRILE (PAN) AND PAN/CARBON-NANOTUBE- (CNT-) BASED CARBON FIBERS

Thomas K. Tsotsis¹, Satish Kumar² Han Gi Chae², Prabhakar Gulgunje², and Bradley Newcomb²

¹Boeing Research & Technology, 5301 Bolsa Ave., Huntington Beach, CA 92647
United States of America

Email: thomas.k.tsotsis@boeing.com, web page: <http://www.boeing.com>

²School of Polymer, Textile and Fiber Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology
801 Ferst Dr., Atlanta, GA 30332, United States of America

Email: satish.kumar@gatech.edu, web page: <http://kumar.mse.gatech.edu/>

Keywords: Carbon fiber, density, hollow, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), polyacrylonitrile (PAN)

ABSTRACT

Hollow polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and PAN/carbon nanotube- (CNT-) based carbon fibers were processed using bi-component fiber spinning in conjunction with gel spinning. Precursor fibers were prepared using an islands-in-a-sea morphology whereby the islands comprised a fugitive material that, when removed during processing, left continuous, hollow regions through the fiber cross section that extended the entire length of each fiber. The remaining sea material, made of polyacrylonitrile, was subsequently converted using conventional processes and equipment into a hollow carbon fiber that has a "honeycomb-like" cross-section and possessed a density that was shown to be significantly lower than conventional solid carbon fibers. Fiber processing, stabilization, and carbonization of these hollow PAN- and PAN/CNT-based carbon fibers were optimized to create fibers with stable cross sections. Precursor fibers, as well as their stabilized and carbonized products were characterized for the structure, morphology, and mechanical properties. Hollow fibers with stiffnesses exceeding those of current state-of-the-art standard-modulus fibers at significantly lower densities were produced. Some unique features of the fiber microstructure will also be described, such as Raman-spectroscopy mapping of the carbonized hollow fiber cross section, which exhibited a strong Raman G-band intensity not only at the outer surface of the carbon fiber but also at the surface of inner walls of the hollow-fiber structure, suggesting that highly ordered graphitic structure was also developed at these regions. The long-term potential benefits and opportunities of this technology will be described such as the ability to tailor fiber properties to a much greater extent than is possible with the current state-of-the-art solid carbon fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

The key goal of this technology development is to reduce carbon-fiber density for lightweight, high-performance structures by producing high-strength and high-modulus carbon fibers of densities in the range of 0.8-1.4 g/cm³ using polyacrylonitrile- (PAN-) based precursor fibers with a hollow structure through bi-component, dry-jet gel spinning with an islands-in-a-sea geometry. Using this technique with PAN as the sea component and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) as the sacrificial islands component, low-density carbon fibers with good mechanical properties have been processed. During stabilization/carbonization, PMMA is removed and the PAN sea component is carbonized. This new geometry of carbon fiber breaks the mold of traditional PAN-based carbon fibers, which have a density of about 1.8 g/cm³. A composite consisting of 60 vol% carbon fibers (with a density of 0.8 g/cm³) and 40 vol% epoxy matrix (with a density of 1.2 g/cm³) will have overall density of 0.96 g/cm³. Thus, structures lighter than water can, in principle, be fabricated. By comparison, the density of current PAN-based carbon fiber/epoxy (60/40 v/v) composites is about 1.54 g/cm³. Figure 1 shows

some sample calculations showing the potential of the present approach for reducing the density of carbon fibers through manipulation of the cross-sectional fiber geometry by modifying the size of the islands and the spacing between them.

In contrast to the approach described herein, the standard method for producing carbon fibers produces solid carbon fibers with densities substantially higher than those targeted in the present work. Furthermore, solid carbon fibers only have highly graphitic structure (which defines the strength and stiffness of the fiber) on the outer portion of the fibers with amorphous structure in the interior whereas the current approach (as will be shown later) can provide graphitic structures at all inner edges, meaning that more graphitic structure can be imparted than possible in solid carbon fibers. Successful development of hollow carbon fibers will allow for pervasive weight savings on all products that use carbon-fiber-based composites.

Figure 1. Sample calculations showing potential weight reduction with different islands-in-a-sea geometries for an islands-in-a-sea geometry with seven islands.

Previous work in carbon fibers

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) is the predominant precursor for carbon fibers. The density of PAN-based carbon fiber is typically between $1.75 - 2.0 \text{ g/cm}^3$ [1]. Recent commercial aircraft, such as the Boeing 787 Dreamliner [2] and Airbus A350 [3] that use substantial amounts of carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRPs), demonstrate the importance of low-density materials in developing high-performance structures. It has also been reported that hollow carbon fibers can be advantageous over solid carbon fibers in applications where compressive properties are critical [4]. Compressive properties and the failure mode of carbon fibers under compression are influenced by the fiber microstructure [5-7] as well as fiber microbuckling [8]. It was also reported that bending stiffness of hollow carbon-fiber-reinforced composites is higher than that of the composites made from solid carbon fibers [9]. Therefore, in a composite that fails due to buckling when subjected to a compressive load, hollow carbon fibers may be advantageous over solid carbon fibers, along with the benefit from reduced density [10].

Previous workers have produced hollow carbon fibers using co-axial electro-spinning and post-treatment [11], as well as by bi-component sheath-core wet spinning with PAN as the sheath and poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) as the core [12], with both types subsequently carbonized into hollow

carbon fibers. Other methods previously studied for producing hollow fibers include a spinneret with C-shaped geometry for the production of hollow precursor fibers produced from pitch [13] or PAN [14, 15]. Fergusson [16] developed the technology to manufacture hollow polymeric fibers using dry-jet wet spinning whereby, while dope flows through a specially designed spinneret, coagulant was injected at the core of the spinneret. Upon subsequent coagulation of the extrudate, fibers possessing a hollow core were formed. Using the same technique, Travis et al. [10], manufactured hollow PAN precursor fibers and converted them into carbon fibers. The hollow carbon fibers manufactured possessed tensile strength and tensile modulus of 0.5 GPa and 249 GPa, respectively. Lee et al. [17], also reported the manufacture of hollow carbon fibers from PAN-based precursors using electro-spinning. Styrene-acrylonitrile (SAN) co-polymer was used as the sacrificial component in the core. The tensile strength of 1.2 GPa and tensile modulus of 60 GPa were obtained in the carbon fibers manufactured by this process.

All previous studies of hollow carbon fibers considered only a sheath-core-type structure. More recently, the islands-in-a-sea geometry made using bi-component spinning has been shown to be useful in the manufacture of polymeric precursor fibers to obtain hollow carbon fibers [18, 19]. If a bi-component precursor fiber is made in such a way that the sheath or sea component is PAN and the islands component is made of a polymer that can be made fugitive to enable its removal during processing, hollow carbon fibers can be obtained. In the present work, an islands-in-a-sea approach was used to manufacture precursor fibers with a multicellular or “honeycomb” cross section. PAN co-polymer and PMMA were used as sea and islands components, respectively. The structure and properties of the precursor fibers and in the resulting hollow carbon fibers are presented and discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Poly(acrylonitrile-co-methacrylic acid) (PAN-co-MAA) co-polymer (4 wt% methacrylic acid) with a viscosity average molecular weight of 250,000 g/mol was obtained from Japan Exlan Co. Ltd (Osaka, Japan) and PMMA with a weight average molecular weight of 350,000 g/mol was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich and used after distillation. Methanol was obtained from VWR International. PAN-co-MAA co-polymer was dried under vacuum at 90°C for 2 days. The PAN-co-MAA/DMAc solution was prepared at a solids concentration of 14.5 g/100 mL DMAc at ~90°C. PMMA/DMAc solution was prepared at a concentration of 32.5 g/100 mL DMAc at ~110 °C.

A bi-component fiber-spinning system supplied by Hills Inc. (Melbourne, FL) was used for the manufacture of precursor fibers. The spin pack used produced bi-component fibers consisting of 7 islands; Chae et al. [20] reported the schematic of the equipment, and that of the geometry of the resulting islands-in-a-sea fibers. Fiber-spinning equipment consisted of two solution reservoirs, one for the PAN-co-MAA solution to be fed as the sea component, and the other for the PMMA solution to be fed as the islands component, as shown in Figure 2. During spinning, the flow rate of PAN-co-MAA solution was maintained at 1.275 cc/min and that of PMMA solution was maintained at 0.225 cc/min. A single-hole spinneret with 200- μ m diameter and L/D ratio of 5 was used. The spinneret temperature was maintained at 80°C. Dry-jet wet spinning was used to obtain the precursor fibers. Methanol was used as the coagulation medium prior to gel-spinning, and was maintained at around 20°C. Based on the combined flow rate of sea and islands components, the linear jet speed was calculated (29.4 m/min) and the take-up speed was set to be 88.2 m/min to obtain a spin-draw ratio of 3. Fiber drawing is shown in Figure 3. The collected as-spun fibers were kept immersed in a methanol bath at room temperature for 3 days followed by multi-step drawing using a hot glycerol bath at 100°C, 135°C, and 160°C.

Figure 2 Schematic of bi-component fiber spinning apparatus (a). Schematic of fiber with islands-in-a sea geometry (b).

Figure 3. Set-up used for fiber drawing.

The drawn fiber was stabilized in air at a constant flow rate of 5 L/min and carbonized in argon at a constant flow rate of 8 L/min using a batch process in a tube furnace manufactured by Micropretics Heaters International (Cincinnati, OH). During stabilization and carbonization, pre-stress was applied to the fibers using a graphite clamp. The pre-stress was calculated based on the precursor fiber diameter and adjusted by varying the number of filaments subjected to stabilization and carbonization. For stabilization, the fibers were heat-treated at two different temperatures (60 min at 260 °C and 20 min at 305 or 325 °C). The heating rate to the pre-determined stabilization temperatures was 5 °C/min. After completing stabilization, the purging gas was switched to argon for 30 min and the furnace was heated up to 1300 °C at a heating rate of 5°C/min followed by isothermal carbonization at 1300 °C for 10 min. In some trials, the stabilized fiber was removed from the furnace and re-clamped to change the pre-stress for carbonization.

Tensile testing of the precursor fibers was done using an RSA-III solids analyzer (TA Instruments, Inc.) at a gauge length of 25.4 mm. The strain rate was 1 %/s for the precursor fiber and the average of 20 tests is reported herein. It is to be noted that the precursor fiber tensile testing was done without PMMA removal, and the tensile properties of these fibers were calculated based on the overall fiber diameter that included PMMA as islands. Effective fiber diameters were calculated using the length-weight method (linear density). In this procedure, bundles of 50 filaments were prepared and their

length and weights were measured. In order to obtain effective fiber diameters from these measurements, the density was assumed to be 1.18 g/cm^3 . Cross-sectional micrographs of as-spun fibers were obtained using a Leica optical microscope. Cross-sectional images of the carbon fibers were obtained using a scanning electron microscope, Zeiss Ultra 60 FE-SEM. The SEM was calibrated using a standard from Ladd Research Industries. Tensile testing of the hollow carbon fibers was also done using RSA-III solids analyzer (TA Instruments, Inc.) at a gauge length of 12.7 mm and at a strain rate of 0.1 %/s with the tensile modulus not corrected for compliance. An effective diameter of the carbon fiber was measured from SEM micrographs using image-analysis software, ImageJ.

Wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) patterns were obtained on a multifilament bundle of precursor fibers, and of carbonized fibers on a Rigaku Micromax-002 diffractometer (operated at 45 kV, 65 mA, $\lambda=0.1542 \text{ nm}$). The diffraction patterns were analyzed using AreaMax V. 1.00 and MDI Jade 6.1. Orientation of the precursor fiber (fc) was determined from the azimuthal scan of diffractions (200, 110) corresponding to $2\theta \sim 16.7^\circ$, and the crystallite size was determined from the equatorial scan of same peak using the Scherrer equation with $K = 0.9$ [21]. The orientation of the carbon fibers (f002) was determined from the azimuthal scan for the peak at $2\theta \sim 25^\circ$. Crystal sizes, $L(002)$ and $L(10)$, in carbon fibers were determined using the Scherrer equation. Raman Spectroscopy was performed on a cross section of the carbonized fiber using a confocal Raman microscope (Alpha-Witek) with a 514-nm laser operated at 3 mW and a 100 \times objective lens. Raman G-band-intensity mapping (line-mapping) was conducted using a 300-nm step size across the cross-section of the hollow carbon fiber. In order to prepare cross sections of a carbonized fiber sample, the fiber was mounted on a TEM grid (Copper 3-post Omniprobe lift-out grid, EMS Inc.) using epoxy (Epo-Tek 353ND, Gatan Inc.). Then, the carbon fiber was thinned using focused-ion-beam (FIB) milling at 30 kV and polishing at 5 kV using FEI NOVA Nanolab 200 FIB/SEM. Few-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were obtained from Continental Carbon Nanotechnologies Inc. (Houston, TX, lot # XOC231U) and Unidym Inc. (Houston, TX, lot # XO122UA). The as-spun fiber was then oxidized and carbonized using varying temperatures, tension levels, and exposure times. All of these were batch-processed with dead weights used, to apply tension.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cross-sectional image of the as-spun fiber shows the distribution of PMMA islands in PAN matrix in Figure 4. It can be seen that overall fiber shape is circular and the islands are fairly uniformly distributed in the sea. As-spun fibers were drawn in multiple stages as described in the experimental section. The draw ratios at the drawing temperatures of 100°C, 135°C, and 160°C were 2.6 \times , 1.5 \times and 1.6 \times , respectively. Tensile properties of the drawn precursor fiber are listed in Table 1, showing that the precursor tensile properties are not as high as for the typical solid PAN precursor fiber [22]. The resulting loss in tensile properties of the precursor fiber can be attributed to the presence of the low mechanical property islands component (PMMA).

Figure 4. Optical micrograph of the as-spun honeycomb precursor fiber. Sea component is PAN-co-MAA co-polymer and islands component (7 islands) is PMMA.

Table 1. Tensile properties and structural parameters of the drawn precursor fiber.

Diameter (μm)	Tensile properties			WAXD	
	Strength (GPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Elongation at break (%)	f_c	Crystallite size ₍₁₁₀₎ (nm)
16.3	0.4 ± 0.03	10.2 ± 1.0	7.3 ± 0.4	0.86	9.5

Stabilization and carbonization conditions, and tensile properties of the hollow carbon fibers are listed in Table 2. The effective diameter of hollow carbon fiber was measured based on the solid area of the fibers from cross-sectional SEM images. For comparison, tensile properties of commercial PAN based solid carbon fiber T300 [23] and IM7 [24] are also listed in Table 2. Tensile moduli of the hollow carbon fibers (Table 2) are calculated based on the equivalent solid-carbon-fiber diameter and are not corrected for compliance. The highest average tensile modulus of the hollow carbon fiber is 368 GPa, which is 60% higher than that of T300 and 33% higher than that of IM7. Based on the overall diameter of the carbon fiber, the hollow carbon fiber modulus is 244 GPa, which is similar to that of T300 (230 GPa). Assuming that the density of the carbonized sea component is similar to that of T300 (1.76 g/cm³), the estimated density of the hollow carbon fiber is about 1.2 g/cm³. Therefore, the specific tensile modulus of the hollow carbon fiber is 209 N/tex (specific modulus = modulus/density). For comparison, the specific tensile moduli of T300 and IM7 are about 130 and 155 N/tex, respectively.

Table 2. Stabilization and carbonization conditions and properties of hollow carbon fibers and commercial carbon fibers.

Trial #	Applied stress* (MPa)	Stabilization temp (°C) / time (min)		Carbonization temp (°C) / time (min)	Effective diameter (μm)	Tensile strength (GPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Elongation to break (%)
		Step 1	Step 2					
1	13.9	260/60	325/20	1300/10	8.3 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 0.8	267 ± 96	0.9 ± 0.3
2	24.9/12.8	260/60	325/20	1300/10	9.6 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.5	342 ± 28	0.7 ± 0.1
3	27/13.9	260/60	325/20	1300/10	10.1 ± 0.3	2.1 ± 0.5	322 ± 25	0.6 ± 0.1
4	24.9/12.8	260/60	305/20	1300/10	9.3 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.6	368 ± 58	0.7
T300	N/A				7	3.5	230	1.5
IM7	N/A				5.2	5.5	276	1.9

* The first value corresponds to the pre-stress applied during stabilization and the second value corresponds to the pre-stress applied during carbonization. For trial 1, the same pre-stress was used for both stabilization and carbonization. The pre-stress is based on the precursor fiber diameter (including islands component).

The tensile modulus is predominantly dependent on the orientation of crystallites along the fiber axis. WAXD analysis of the hollow carbon fiber shows that the full width at half maximum intensity (FWHM) of the azimuthal scan at $2\theta \sim 25^\circ$ is smaller than that of T300 but larger than that of IM7 carbon fiber (Table 3). This structural orientation information suggests that the overall orientation of crystallites in the hollow carbon fiber is higher than that in T300 but lower than that in IM7. However, the tensile modulus of the hollow carbon fiber is significantly higher than that of both T300 and IM7, suggesting that the structure of the hollow carbon fiber is different from that of the solid carbon fiber. Therefore, Raman spectroscopy was carried out on a honeycomb carbon fiber cross section, as shown in Figure 5 (a). As noted in the experimental section, Raman line-mapping was conducted using the G-band peak position ($\sim 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which corresponds to the graphitic structure in the carbon fiber.

Points A to H in Figure 5 (b) correspond to the points A to H in Figure 5 (a). It can be seen from Figure 5 (b) that the intensity of the graphitic G-band peak is higher at the outer wall edges as well as in the regions surrounding the removed islands than elsewhere in the fiber, suggesting higher graphitic order in these regions. Figure 5 (c) and 2(d) provide the SEM image and schematic of the honeycomb carbon fiber cross-section, respectively. Higher orientation in the skin region of carbon fibers as compared to the core region has been reported in the literature [25]. Watt et al. [26] ascribed the origin of skin-core structure in carbon fibers to the process of oxygen diffusion during stabilization of precursor fibers. In the case of hollow carbon fibers, along with the outer walls, inner walls will be analogous to the skin region. In addition, the higher molecular orientation can be expected at the surface of spinneret and between the components for bi-component spinning. Therefore, higher graphitic order near wall edges than elsewhere is expected and this may be the reason for high tensile modulus of the hollow carbon fibers as compared to the commercial carbon fibers. It has been also reported that the tensile modulus of carbon fiber is influenced more by the skin region than by the core region. Diefendorf et al. [27] reported that due to variation in axial preferred orientation, most of the load is carried by the skin upon loading the carbon fibers. Liu et al. [28] also reported that the tensile modulus of carbon fibers is more influenced by the degree of graphitization of the surface of carbon fiber than that of its core. Lastly, Wang et al. [29] show the Raman spectroscopy for a solid carbon fiber clearly showing the presence of high orientation only on the outer portion of the fiber.

Figure 5. Optical micrograph of the hollow-carbon-fiber cross section prepared by FIB milling, (a), and Raman G-band (1590 cm^{-1}) intensity variation across the carbon-fiber cross section along the line shown in (a), (b). The alphabetical notes (A – H) in (b) correspond to those in (a), and represent the position of the fiber cross section. SEM image, (c), and schematic description of the carbon-fiber cross section, (d).

Figure 6. Raman spectroscopy of a solid carbon fiber [29].

In Figure 7, the specific tensile modulus of the hollow carbon fiber is plotted against density. For comparison, the specific tensile moduli of high-performance commercial fibers are also presented in Figure 7 [23, 24, 30-32]. It should also be noted that the tensile moduli of commercial fibers are corrected for compliance while that of the hollow carbon fiber in the current study was not corrected for compliance. Therefore, further improvements in hollow carbon fiber tensile modulus can be expected. As seen from Figure 7, the low-density carbon fibers from the present work fall in the lower range of densities of various high-performance fibers and the specific tensile modulus of the current low-density carbon fiber is the highest amongst all high-performance fibers.

Figure 7. Specific tensile moduli of high-performance fibers as a function of density. Black circles and blue triangles represent high-performance polymeric fibers and commercial carbon fibers, respectively. Hollow (“Honeycomb”) carbon fiber (red diamond point) has low density with intermediate specific modulus.

In Figure 8, a hollow carbon fiber produced in the present work is compared directly against several commercial carbon fibers to compare the measurement of the full width at half maximum using X-ray diffraction. This figure shows that the value for the hollow fiber that fits the general trend observed in the commercial fibers, suggesting that the degree of orientation within the fiber that gives rise to increased modulus is approximately the same for solid or hollow carbon fibers with similar moduli.

Figure 8. X-ray diffraction results showing full width at half maximum (FWHM) for several commercial fibers and for a hollow carbon fiber produced in the present work.

Figure 9 shows several cross sections of hollow PAN/CNT-based carbon fibers produced in the present work, which are believed by the authors to be the first multicellular, hollow carbon/CNT fibers ever produced. These images show that the lessons learned in producing hollow fibers from PAN-only precursor could be successfully applied to produce PAN/CNT-based fibers with reasonably good cross-sectional quality. Work with these fibers is in its early stages and processing and, hence, mechanical properties, still need to be optimized.

Figure 9. SEM images of hollow-fiber cross sections made using PAN/CNT.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main goals of the present work were to obtain affordable hollow carbon fibers that are continuously producible in large volumes with properties between standard carbon fibers and carbon nanotubes and good compression-strength retention with the processes developed to produce these fibers transitionable to industrial carbon-fiber manufacturing and capable of utilizing the same, existing infrastructure. To date, all results indicated that these goals are achievable and it has already been demonstrated by fabricating PAN-based precursor fibers with islands-in-a-sea geometry with good distribution of the seven islands in the sea that the processes used are indeed compatible with large-scale industrialization. Further, the best hollow carbon fiber manufactured thus far possessed a tensile modulus of 209 N/tex, which is 60% higher than that of the commercial solid carbon fiber T300 (130 N/tex), meeting another of the stated goals. The high tensile modulus of the hollow carbon fibers was attributed to improved graphitic order at the wall edges as evidenced from G-band mapping of the honeycomb carbon fiber cross-section using Raman spectroscopy. This is the first result of its kind in showing graphitic alignment within a carbon fiber and not solely on the outer surface. Additionally, carbon fibers with specific tensile modulus of up to 209 N/tex are by a large margin the highest fiber modulus reported for a material with density of less than 1.2 g/cm³. Hollow carbon/CNT fibers have also been produced, demonstrating that such fibers are also feasible.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Financial support for this work from the Boeing Company and the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (FA9550-10-1-0475) is gratefully acknowledged.

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